

POLITICAL SCIENCES

LEGITIMACY OF USING FORCE IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

Ispas A.M.

*Ph.D Candidate in Informations and National Security
"Carol I" National Defence University, Bucharest*

LEGITIMITATEA UTILIZĂRII FORȚEI ÎN RELAȚIILE INTERNAȚIONALE

Ispas A.M.

*Doctorand în Informații și Securitate Națională
Universitatea Națională de Apărare "Carol I", București*

Abstract

States have the obligation to look for methods that do not involve resorting to force to resolve disputes, being forced at the same time to refrain from resorting to the threat of force, but also to cooperate to ensure a stable global security environment. The use of armed force, however, remains a monopoly of states, so that only they can resort to legitimate coercion against acts of armed violence affecting national or international security. The only way that individuals have to use the armed force in the state legal order is legitimate defense, justifiable cause provided by the criminal law, exonerating liability.

Abstract

Statele au obligația de a căuta metode care nu presupun recurgerea la forță pentru soluționarea diferendelor, fiind nevoite în același timp să se abțină inclusiv de a recurge la amenințarea cu forța, dar și de a coopera pentru asigurarea unui mediu de securitate stabil pe plan global. Utilizarea forței armate rămâne însă un monopol al statelor, astfel încât numai acestea pot apela la constrângerea legitimă împotriva actelor de violență armată care afectează securitatea națională sau internațională. Singura modalitate pe care indivizii o au pentru a utiliza forța armată în ordinea juridică statală este legitima apărare, cauză justificativă prevăzută de legea penală, exoneratoare de răspundere.

Keywords: conflicts, military force, self-defense, sovereignty, international security, United Nations.

Cuvinte cheie: conflicte, forță armată, legitimă apărare, suveranitate, securitate internațională, Organizația Națiunilor Unite.

Introduction

Prohibitions aimed at excluding the use of armed force have developed over time as a result of marked progress in international law, so that the possibility of waging war has ceased to be seen as a sovereign prerogative of states. Currently, they are obliged to settle disputes peacefully, which is why armed force can no longer be used except in cases provided for by the UN Charter.[1]

Starting with the First World War, the international community began to show its interest in creating centralized and permanent institutional mechanisms to ensure the maintenance of peace. In this sense, the Covenant of the League of Nations was adopted, but the document did not expressly prohibit resorting to war, but established certain procedural rules that allowed states to use armed force, among which can be mentioned: the obligation to submit the dispute to arbitration, to allow a period of three months from the adoption of the arbitral decision before resorting to war or applying economic sanctions to the aggressor state.

Later, between the two world wars, the prohibitions on the use of force in relations between states evolved through the development of these rules. The Briand-Kellogg Pact adopted in 1928 represented one of the important legal instruments in the field, because it expressly prohibited the war of aggression.

According to him, the parties pledged to renounce war as an instrument of national policy and declared

themselves ready to resolve by peaceful means conflicts of any nature and whatever their origin.[2]

Currently, the UN Charter is the foundation of the prohibition of the use of force in international relations. According to art. 1, the main objective of the organization aims at "maintaining peace and international security, as well as adopting collective measures to prevent or remove threats against peace and to repress acts of aggression".[3]

Considering the new categories of conflicts that cause permanent changes in international relations, including the current war between Russia and Ukraine, the topic under analysis aims to identify the situations and conditions in which the legitimacy of the use of force can currently be invoked to settle these differences, as well as the mechanisms accepted by the UN legal system, which would provide the legal benchmarks for their application by the military during international missions.

The methodology of the present research is reflected by the use of the historical and analytical method that gives us the opportunity to notice the evolution of the concept of self-defense in interstate relations, but also of the international normative framework in the field, by identifying the relevant data from articles, doctrine or legislation. These contribute to the identification of some legal solutions that must be adopted in the situation where the right to self-defense is invoked abusively by the states, exceeding the legal limits, thus destabilizing the sovereignty of the states.

At the same time, through the method of deduction, the legal qualification of the facts is established, so that from the content of the topic addressed, it follows that the theoretical aspects can be found in practical situations.

Legitimate defense in the international legal order

The first accepted exception to the principle of the prohibition of the use of armed force is that provided for in Article 51 of the Charter, which allows any UN member state to react immediately in the event of an attack against it, based on the right of self-defense, without waiting for the adoption a decision by the Security Council.

Given that the Council's activity can be blocked by its exercise of the right of veto, thus becoming ineffective to protect a UN member against acts of aggression, art. 51 gives states the freedom to react on their own against imminent armed attacks.

However, the State's freedom to act is limited by its obligation to inform the Council of the measures it has adopted, which shall not affect its right to undertake any other measures it deems necessary for the maintenance of international peace and security.

Article 51 must be interpreted in conjunction with art. 2 para. (4) of the Charter, which prohibits both the use of force and the threat of force in international relations.

The use of force can be accepted internationally only against those who have violated fundamental international values, to protect all members of the community, not allowing the right to self-defense to be exercised in an arbitrary or abusive manner.

In order to be able to resort to self-defense, the state that invokes it must prove the existence of a violation of a legal obligation from which it benefits and which has caused damage to it. At the same time, the measures taken on the basis of legitimate defense must be proportionate to the threat.

This rule was stipulated in the *Caroline case*, in which the US asked the British government to justify the destruction of an American ship by British nationals[4]. In this dispute it was decided that the invocation of the right of self-defence did not depend on the situation in which Britain was the subject of an armed attack and it was accepted that self-defence was anticipated in the face of the threat of an armed attack.

Although this case is part of international jurisprudence, as a source of contemporary international law, being often invoked by states, including in the Nuremberg trial, when Germany claimed in its defense that the invasion of Norway was imposed by an act of preventive self-defense, in The UN Charter neither the threat of force nor the imminent attack justifies the use of force. The theory of the "inherent right" of legitimate defense is not recognized by the Security Council either, because it can generate abuses or errors that can be considered threats to world security.

Thus, self-defense must not be excessive or unreasonable, which is why a declaration of war that is not followed by an actual, actual attack does not justify armed retaliation in the exercise of the right to self-defense.

The measures taken must be instantaneous, irresistible, without the victim having a choice of means or time to deliberate, meaning that all measures taken in self-defense must be an immediate response to the assault, otherwise being considered reprisals.[5]

The interpretation of the limits to which legitimate defense can extend according to the UN Charter, especially the scope of the notion of "armed aggression", is controversial.

The confusion occurs on the basis of the way in which the right to legitimate defense must be delimited, either by referring to the provisions of art. 2 para. (4), either to those of art. 51 of the Charter. Art. 2 para. (4) refers to the general prohibition of the threat or use of force against the territorial integrity of a state. But, art. 51 is the only one that regulates the conditions of invoking legitimate defense, which does not refer to the use of force in general, but to the use of armed force.

If the provisions regarding the use of legitimate defense were to be interpreted extensively, it would mean abusing this right, by eliminating the rule regarding the prohibition of the use of force, and there is the possibility of creating an opportunity to undermine the main responsibility of the Security Council, to maintain international peace and security.[6]

Therefore, self-defense can only exist as a response to armed force, by virtue of art. 51 of the Charter.

According to art. 39 of the Charter, the Council has the competence to determine the existence or not of a threat to international security, but it must not extend this right indefinitely, by cataloging a crisis situation existing on the territory of a state as a threat to international peace .

It is necessary that the notion of "right to individual or collective self-defence" be defined in much clearer terms as to when a state can take preventive action to protect itself against a violation of its sovereignty as a result of an attack armed imminent or that may be perceived as such, when there is convincing evidence that after an attack has already been carried out, the enemy is preparing to attack again, given that some states have exercised this right in advance, as is the case US through military intervention in Afghanistan and Iraq.

Although in art. 51 of the UN Charter acts of terrorism are not expressly mentioned in the category of armed attacks, the Security Council admitted through resolutions no. 1368 and no. 1373 of 2001 that armed attack also includes terrorist attack, expanding the interpretation of the provisions of the Charter according to its political interests.

In Resolution no. 1368 (2001) The Security Council asserted its jurisdiction, invoking that there had been a threat to international peace and security within the meaning of the UN Charter, and condemned the September 11, 2001 attacks in New York, calling on states to cooperate in bringing the perpetrators of the attack to justice.[7] Pursuant to the same resolution, the Council recognizes the right to self-defense according to the Charter.

In Resolution no. 1373 (2001), it confirms its previous position regarding self-defense and that acts of

international terrorism are a threat to international security[8].

The Council justifies its competence by a reference to the principle that the UN General Assembly established in its declaration of 1970 (res. 2625 XXV), which it reaffirmed in its resolution no. 1189 (1998), according to which "every state has the obligation to refrain from organizing and encouraging acts of terrorism on the territory of another state". [9]

Under this pretext, the Council imposes a series of measures regarding the blocking of the financing of terrorism and asks the states to take a series of measures to combat it.

In order to avoid this legislative loophole in the future, an express provision should be inserted in the Charter to establish whether the right to self-defense can be invoked on the basis of the launch of an anticipated attack, before the aggressor state has actually undertaken the act of aggression.

The right to self-defense was also invoked in the case that Nicaragua filed against the United States at the International Court of Justice in The Hague in 1986. During the case, the conditions for exercising this right were analyzed and it was considered that in order to be invoked, it is necessary to take into account the necessity and proportionality of the attack, the anticipated attack for the purpose of self-defense of a state being justified only if against that state there is the imminence of launching an attack by another state.[10]

Also, the right to self-defense was recognized by the Security Council through Resolution no. 660 (1990), in response to Iraq's armed attack on Kuwait and affirmed the determination to restore Kuwait's sovereignty, independence, and territorial integrity, requiring states to adopt measures and cooperate in this regard. Also on the basis of this resolution it was established that the annexation of territories is not legal for any reason.[11]

The distinction between a preventive attack and an anticipated one should be expressly stipulated in the Charter, so that its states can no longer abuse the right to self-defense. Therefore, it can be considered that an attack is anticipated in the situation where there is evidence of a plan containing specific actions of aggression on the part of another state, while a preventive attack is the one directed against a potential, abstract danger, regarding which there is no concrete evidence of preparation of an attack, which can be categorized as illegal.[12]

Security Council involvement in limiting the use of armed force

The second exception to the possibility of using armed force in international relations is provided in Chapters VI and VII of the UN Charter which refer to the monopoly of the Security Council to decide on the international use of force.

Art. 53 of the Charter highlights the right of the Council to use regional agreements or bodies to apply coercive measures under its authority. Thus, no power that is not part of the region will be able to oppose its right of veto in the Council, to a coercive action of a regional nature.[13]

Action may be taken under an agreement or regional body, even when armed force has not been used, but a situation involving the maintenance of international peace and security arises. Using an action based on art. 53 does not contravene the right to invoke legitimate defense according to art. 51, but it is preferable to resort to art. 53 because the parties to the agreement or the participants in the regional body have no obligation to inform the Council about the action taken, as long as no coercive measure is applied.

In this case, economic sanctions are not subject to the authorization of the Security Council, nor are peace-keeping operations organized with the consent of the state on whose territory they are carried out.

The Security Council has the right to commit UN forces and act directly against threats to international peace and security. In the decision-making process, permanent members are vested with a right of veto through which they can block the adoption of certain decisions. Regarding the adoption of decisions, it cannot be subject to any external control, from the General Assembly or the International Court of Justice.

The Council cannot objectively establish the existence of a threat to peace because states invoke self-defense when they find the existence of acts of armed aggression, and the exercise of the right of veto prevents it from taking coercive measures, a situation that has the effect of escalating conflicts between states by their determination to resort to illicit actions.

Such actions taken on the basis of an erroneous interpretation of the invocation of legitimate defense have been criticized throughout time.

The theory that a state would have the right to take preventive measures against an aggression that did not take place or to remove a dictatorial regime or establish the recognition of human rights, was invoked by Israel to trigger the Six Day War against Egypt. The action did not fulfill the conditions underlying the invocation of the right to self-defense, being considered an act of armed aggression.

Another theory under which legitimate defense is abusively invoked is the one related to the right of humanitarian intervention. This theory is based on the idea that a state has the right to use force to protect individuals, victims of abuse of power. Such an argument was invoked by the US in the Iraq war, to remove from power the regime imposed by Saddam Hussein, so as to achieve the transition to a democratic government established by the Americans, following in this context the exploitation of oil resources by the countries allies under the pretext of rebuilding Iraq.

Given that self-defense can only exist as a form of response to armed aggression, all these actions contravene art. 51 of the UN Charter and can be classified as abusive and illegal acts.

The introduction of the right of veto in the UN Charter led to the creation of inequality between states, as it allowed permanent members to block the adoption of any resolutions, including those that might affect them, thus placing them above the provisions of the Charter by enjoying immunity from measures that could be enacted against them.

Inequality is also manifested in terms of the limited capacity of the states to support the military operations authorized by the Council, as well as in relation to their financial contributions, which made the permanent members the main donors of funds to the Organization.

If the acceptance of some states as members of the UN has been delayed for a certain period, this has been for reasons of political interest, unrelated to the conditions of membership stipulated in the Charter, and no member has ever been excluded, although there are states whose actions they are denounced by the UN, but also by other international organizations, such as the case of Russia following the outbreak of the conflict in Ukraine.

The war started by Russia in Ukraine in 2022 once again raised the question of giving up the right of veto and reforming the UN Security Council. However, sanctioning Russia by excluding it from the Council involves a complicated procedure, which runs into a series of legislative inconsistencies, but also the political interests of the other permanent members, especially the USA.

Although it violates the rights to self-determination and territorial integrity of a sovereign state, Russia wants to keep Ukraine in its sphere of influence, especially to prevent Ukraine from joining NATO or deepening relations with the EU.

The exclusion of Russia from the Security Council is a sanction allowed by the UN Charter, according to art. 6, but it is a difficult wish to achieve, considering that the decisions of the Council must be approved by at least nine members, but they can be rejected if only one of the permanent members exercises his right of veto. In this case, it is impossible for Russia to vote against its own interests.

Taking into account the fact that some of the permanent members represent some of the great economic powers of the world, their decisions influence the settlement of disputes. In order to create an equality between states in the adoption of decisions, it is necessary to remove from the Charter the distinction between permanent and non-permanent members, thus achieving a complete reform of the Security Council, by removing its monopoly, in which case the resolutions of the General Assembly should acquire binding legal force.

Although the veto regulation has many disadvantages, it can also be considered to have an advantage in that it prevents any of the permanent members from gaining the support of a sufficient number of Council members to violate the Charter, given that its decisions are adopted by the vote of nine members, according to art. 27 of the Charter.

Thus, the right of veto allows blocking the adoption of a decision contrary to the law, being a means for the Council to control itself, to avoid any direct military confrontation of the permanent members.[14]

Conclusions

Except in cases of self-defense or enforcement of agreements between states, legal norms and practice make the use of armed force an attribute of international organizations, reflecting the international community's interest in using force to benefit the citizens of states.

However, all of the Charter's prohibitions on the use of armed force have so far failed to prevent the outbreak of wars, given that its provisions are outdated and should be adapted to the new categories of crises faced by states. Legislative loopholes create more and more opportunities for the escalation of conflicts and the satisfaction of political or economic interests for the great powers.

The centralized system of maintaining international peace and security established by the Charter and the paralysis of the functioning of the Security Council by exercising the right of veto of the permanent members, but also the total lack of adhesion of the states to the peaceful settlement of disputes, explain the reasons why states resort to force in order to promote their own interests. In some cases they avoid resorting to obvious forms of aggression and seek to justify their actions through the presumed exceptions of international law to the prohibition of the use of armed force.

References

1. Geamănu G., *Drept internațional contemporan*, Bucharest, 1975, p. 186.
2. Briand-Kellogg Pact 1928, art. 1-2, <https://www.uni-marburg.de/de/icwc/zentrum/pdfs/briandkelloggact.pdf>.
3. UN Charta, art. 1, <https://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocumentAfis/19362>.
4. The Caroline Case, https://avalon.law.yale.edu/19th_century/br-1842d.asp.
5. Macdonald R.J., *L'emploi de la force par les Etats en droit international*, în *Droit international (Bilan et perspectives)*, tome 2, red. gen. M. Bedjaoui, A Pedone Publishing House, Paris, p. 775.
6. Anghel Ion M., Anghel Viorel I., *Regulile războiului și dreptul umanitar*, Lumina Lex Publishing House, Bucharest, 2003, p. 15.
7. Resolution 1368 (2001) / adopted by the Security Council at its 4370th meeting, on 12 September 2001, pct. 1-5, <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/448051>.
8. Resolution 1373 (2001) / adopted by the Security Council at its 4385th meeting, on 28 September 2001, preambul par. 2, https://www.unodc.org/pdf/crime/terrorism/res_1373_english.pdf.
9. Resolution 1189 (1998) / adopted by the Security Council at its 3915th meeting, on 13 August 1998, preambul par. 5, <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/258404>.
10. Case concerning military and paramilitary activities in and against Nicaragua, June 27 1986, ICJ Reports 1986, parag. 176, pp. 94-95, <https://www.icj-cij.org/public/files/case-related/70/070-19860627-JUD-01-00-EN.pdf>.
11. Resolution 660 (1990) / adopted by the Security Council at its 2932th meeting, on 2 August 1990, <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/94220>.
12. Lascu A.L., *Crima de agresiune-Un updating sau un upgrading necesar*, *Universul Juridic Magazine*, no. 2, february 2016, p. 129.
13. UN Charta, art. 53.
14. Sur. S., *Relații internaționale*, 7-th Edition, C.H. Beck Publishing House, Bucharest, 2021, p. 435.